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Studies on combining ability for Horticultural traits in Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp)

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The present investigation was undertaken to study the type of gene action involved for green pod yield and its components in cowpea and to estimate the general combining ability and specific combining ability of parents and crosses, respectively. The experimental material comprised of six lines viz., 2012/COPBVAR-2, 2012/COPBVAR-3, 2012/COPBVAR-5, 2014/COPBVAR-4, 2014/COPBVAR-5 and 2014/COPBVAR-6 and four testers viz. Gomti, PusaKomal, KashiKanchan and ArkaGarima which were crossed in line x tester mating design to generate F₁ hybrids. The significance of both gca and sca variance for most of the characters indicated that both additive as well as non-additive types of gene actions were involved in the inheritance of these traits. The gca effects of parents suggested that 2014/COPBVAR-4, 2012/COPBVAR-2, 2014/COPBVAR-5 and KashiKanchan were good combiners for different yield components like number of flowers per cluster, number of pods per cluster, per cent pod set, number of pods per plant and days to last harvest. The ArkaGarima, 2014/COPBVAR-5 and 2014/COPBVAR-4 were good general combiner for days to 50% flowering and KashiKanchan, 2014/COPBVAR-5 and 2012/COPBVAR-2 for green pod yield per plant. No single parent was found to be good for all the traits. Based on specific combining ability effects of the hybrids, the cross combination 2014/COPBVAR-5 x Gomti was found to be the best combination both for number of pods per plant and green pod yield per plant. The other best specific combinations were 2012/COPBVAR-3 x PusaKomal, 2012/COPBVAR-5 x PusaKomal and 2012/COPBVAR-2 x ArkaGarima with high positive sca effects and high mean for green pod yield per plant. These promising parents can be used in future breeding programmes and the crosses may be exploited for isolation of transgressive segregants from the segregating generations of these crosses for further improvement of pod yield in cowpea.

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Maintenance and characterization of Indian aloe germplasm of Thar desert under hot arid agro-climate

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Indian aloe or *guarpatha* (*Aloe barbadensis*) is one of the most popular and multiple-use crop-plants of Thar desert. Two distinct forms of Indian aloe were collected during 1994 for conservation as regional germplasm at ICAR-CIAH, Bikaner. From the intensive survey studies during 1994 to 1996 on native and underexploited crop plants, it was documented that *guarpatha* is one of the most common, home-stead and perennial vegetables. The studies on Indian aloe in the district of Bikaner, Churu, Nagaur and Jodhpur of Rajasthan demonstrated that there are two forms i.e. sweet and bitter types, which are used widely by desert dwellers. It is much liked for various culinary, pickle, sweets and juices preparations. During 1994, suckers of two population i.e. sweet type for vegetable purpose (AHAB-S-1) and bitter type for making medicinal products were collected and conserved. During 2001, one more germplasm of *Aloe vera* was collected from Kutch area of Gujarat, which is bitter type. During 2017, the collected germplasm was studied at ICAR-CIAH, Bikaner for the maintenance, conservation and for their potential commercialization. The uniform suckers from both the germplasm (AHAB-S-1 and AHAB-B-1) were collected from progeny block of nursery and planted with drip irrigation for characterization and evaluation. The plants of AHAB-S-1 are medium in growth and spreading in nature. Leaves are fleshy, green in colour and about 50 cm in length, while the plants of AHAB-B-1 are medium in growth and upright in nature. Leaves are thick, fleshy and light green in colour and are 50 cm in length. However, detailed characterization and evaluation for quality and yield parameters is in progress.